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INTEGRALNING BA'ZI TATBIQLARI

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7466443>

Annotasiya: Maqolada aniq integrallarni hisoblashning umumiy va xususiy hollariga qaratilgan. Maqolada toq funksiyalar orqali hisoblash, integralni integrallar yig'indisiga ajratish bilan, integralni yangi o'zgaruvchi kiritish usullari bilan hisoblash ko'rsatilgan. Bundan tashqari integrallarning tadbiqu ham keltirilgan.

Tayanch so'zlar: Aniq integral, Nyuton-Leybnis formulasi, toq funksiya, differensial, topmoq, chegaralangan, ko'phad, ayniyat, umumiy ko'paytuvchi, argument, yechim, bajarmoq, almashtirmoq. Yuza

Annotation: The article illustrates theorems concerning the methods of solving integral coefficient of polynomials in specific and common ways finding the solutions by odd functions, separating the sum of integrals and methods and adding changeable integers are shown in the following article.

Keywords: Definite integral, Newton-Leibniz formula, odd function, differential, to find, to be bounded, polynomial, identity, common factor, argument, solution, to carry out, to rearrange, surface.

Аннотация: Статия основана общих и частых случаев интеграла, выбора олимпиады точного и интегрального вычислений. В публикации показаны способы вычислений интеграл нечетных функций методом в ведение новой переменной.

Ключевые слова: Определенный интеграл, нечетная функция, дифференциал, найти, быть ограниченным, многочлен, тождество, общий множитель, аргумент, решение, выполнять, преобразовать, поверхность

1-masala. OX o'qi, $x = -1, x = 2$ to'g'ri chiziqlar va $y = 9 - x^2$ parabola bilan chegaralangan egri chiziqli trapetsiyaning yuzini hisoblang.

Masalaning shartga ko'ra chizmani chizamiz. Yuzani quyidagicha topamiz:

$$S = \int_{-1}^2 (9 - x^2) dx = \left(9x - \frac{x^3}{3} \right) \Big|_{-1}^2 = \left(9 \cdot 2 - \frac{2^3}{3} \right) - \left(9 \cdot (-1) - \frac{(-1)^3}{3} \right) = 18 - \frac{8}{3} + 9 - \frac{1}{3} = 27 - 3 = 24$$

2-masala: $y = x^2$, $y = 2x - x^2$ parabolalar va OX o'qi bilan chegaralangan figuraning yuzini toping.

Yechish: $y = x^2$, $y = 2x - x^2$ funksiyalarning grafiklarini yasaymiz. $x^2 = 2x - x^2$ tenglamadan bu grafiklarning kesishmasi nuqtalari (0;0) va (1;1) larni topamiz.

Demak, izlayotgan yuza bu trapetsiyalarning yuzalari yig'ndisiga teng:

$$S = \int_0^1 x^2 dx + \int_1^2 (2x - x^2) dx = \frac{x^3}{3} \Big|_0^1 + \left(x^2 - \frac{x^3}{3} \right) \Big|_1^2 = \frac{1}{3} + 2^2 - \frac{2^3}{3} - 1^2 + \frac{1}{3} = 3 + \frac{2}{3} - \frac{8}{3} = 3 - \frac{6}{3} = 3 - 2 = 1$$

Hajmlarni integrallar yordamida hisoblash.

Agar jismning Ox o'qqa perpendikulyar bo'lgan ko'ndalang kesimining $S(x)$ yuzi ma'lum bo'lsa, uning hajmini

$$V = \int_a^b S(x) dx \quad (1)$$

formula yordamida hisoblash mumkin.

Agar jism yuqoridan $y = f(x)$ uzluksiz ($a < x < b$) funksiya grafigining AB yoyi

bilan chegaralangan aABb egri chiziqli trapetsiya Ox o'q atrofida aylantirishdan hosil qilingan bo'lsa, uning hajmi $S(x) = \pi r^2 = \pi y^2 = \pi f^2(x)$

bo'lgani uchun $V_x = \pi \int_a^b y^2 dx$ yoki

$$V_x = \pi \int_a^b f^2(x) dx \quad (2) \text{ formula yorda-}$$

mida hisoblanadi.

Masala: R radiusli sharning hajmini toping.

Yechish: Shar markazini koordinatalar boshi uchun qabul qilamiz. xy tekislik R radiusli sharni

tenglama bilan beriladigan aylana bo'yi-ga kesadi.

x o'qidan yuqorida joylashgan yarim aylana $y = f(x) = \sqrt{R^2 - x^2}$, $-R \leq x \leq R$ teng-lama bilan ifodalanadi. Shuning uchun

$$\text{shar hajmi: } V = \pi \int_{-R}^R (\sqrt{R^2 - x^2})^2 dx =$$

$$= \pi \int_{-R}^R (R^2 - x^2) dx = \pi \left(R^2 x - \frac{x^3}{3} \right) \Big|_{-R}^R =$$

$$= \pi \left(R^2 \cdot R - \frac{R^3}{3} \right) - \pi \left(R^2 \cdot (-R) - \frac{(-R)^3}{3} \right) = \pi \left(R^3 - \frac{R^3}{3} + R^3 - \frac{R^3}{3} \right) = \pi \left(\frac{2R^3}{3} + \frac{2R^3}{3} \right) = \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3$$

Foydalanilgan asosiy adabiyotlar:

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